

Endodontic sealer extrusion with secondary osteomyelitis-related bone sequestration: A case report

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Abstract

Endodontic treatment is a predictable therapeutic approach; however, procedural complications may significantly compromise biological healing and long-term tooth survival. This case report describes a severe post-endodontic complication resulting in tooth extraction and inflammatory bone sequestration. A 48-year-old male patient presented with persistent pain originating from the mandibular right second molar. Root canal treatment was performed over three sessions, including calcium hydroxide medication and definitive obturation using a single-cone technique. Radiographic verification revealed root perforation and extrusion of sealer into the periapical tissues of both roots. Despite conservative postoperative management, the clinical course was characterized by persistent pain, progressive tooth mobility, and radiographically evident osteolysis. Extraction was therefore indicated. Intraoperatively, the tooth was removed atraumatically together with a loosely attached bone sequestrum. Histopathological examination confirmed a purulent inflammatory process associated with foreign material and granulation tissue. Postoperative healing was uneventful, and radiographic follow-up demonstrated favorable bone regeneration. This case highlights the potential for obturation-related complications to trigger sustained inflammatory bone reactions and underscores the importance of timely risk-based decisionmaking. When biological deterioration and foreign-body-induced inflammation coexist, extraction may represent a justified and definitive therapeutic endpoint rather than a failure of endodontic care.

Keywords

endodontic complications, root canal sealer extrusion, periapical inflammation, inflammatory bone sequestration, tooth extraction

Introduction

Despite continuous improvements in endodontic materials, instrumentation, and treatment protocols, tooth extraction remains a relevant outcome following root canal therapy in adult patients. Evidence from large-scale, population-based analyses demonstrates that postendodontic extraction is most frequently associated with persistent

apical pathology, inadequate technical quality of the root canal filling, and insufficient coronal restoration, rather than being an immediate consequence of the endodontic procedure itself. In their register-based cohort study, (Fransson et al. 2021) identified the presence of apical periodontitis at the time of root canal filling as one of the strongest predictors of subsequent extraction, underscoring the critical role of unresolved infection in determining

long-term tooth survival (Fransson et al. 2021). Furthermore, teeth with suboptimal obturation length or density, particularly in anatomically complex molars, exhibited a significantly increased risk of extraction, reflecting both biological vulnerability and technical challenges. The authors also highlighted the importance of adequate post-endodontic restoration, as teeth lacking proper coronal sealing were markedly more prone to extraction (Fransson et al. 2021). Collectively, these findings indicate that extraction following endodontic complications represents a multifactorial therapeutic decision, typically adopted when persistent infection, compromised tooth structure, or limited restorative potential render retreatment outcomes unpredictable. Beyond biological and technical determinants, certain endodontic complications raise important ethical and medico-legal considerations, particularly when they result in irreversible structural damage to the tooth. Root canal stripping represents one such complication, characterized by excessive removal of dentin along the canal wall, most frequently in curved or anatomically complex roots. As discussed by (Ciobanu et al. 2016), canal stripping occupies a nuanced position between an unavoidable procedural accident and potential malpractice, depending on factors such as case selection, operator experience, and adherence to accepted clinical protocols (2). The authors emphasize that while some stripping events may occur despite appropriate technique, the resulting structural compromise often significantly limits the prognosis of the affected tooth, increasing susceptibility to vertical root fracture and persistent infection. In such scenarios, the decision to proceed with extraction may reflect not only a biological necessity but also a responsible therapeutic and ethical choice, aimed at preventing further complications and ensuring patient safety (Ciobanu et al. 2016).

In addition to ethical considerations, a broad spectrum of procedural and post-procedural complications has been systematically described in contemporary endodontic literature. Bhuva and Ikram (2020) categorize endodontic complications into instrumentation-related errors, obturation-related deficiencies, and biologically driven failures, emphasizing that many of these events are inter-related rather than isolated occurrences. Instrument separation, canal transportation, perforations, and inadequate cleaning and shaping may compromise effective microbial control, while obturation errors such as underfilling, overfilling, or poor condensation can facilitate persistent periapical inflammation. The authors further highlight that the clinical impact of these complications is strongly influenced by tooth anatomy, operator experience, and case complexity, particularly in multi-rooted teeth. When such factors converge and lead to unresolved infection, structural weakening, or recurrent symptoms, the predictability of retreatment diminishes substantially, thereby justifying extraction as a definitive therapeutic approach aimed at eliminating the source of infection and preventing further tissue destruction (Bhuva and Ikram (2020)).

Irrigation-related events constitute another important category of endodontic complications with potential

implications for treatment outcome and tooth survival. Hülsmann et al. (2007) provide a comprehensive analysis of complications arising during root canal irrigation, including chemical injury to periapical tissues, apical extrusion of irrigants, postoperative pain, tissue necrosis, and delayed healing (Hülsmann et al. 2007). The authors emphasize that improper needle placement, excessive irrigant pressure, and anatomical variations such as wide apical foramina or root resorption significantly increase the risk of irrigant extrusion beyond the root canal system. Such incidents may provoke acute inflammatory reactions, soft tissue damage, and exacerbation of periapical pathology, thereby compromising the biological environment necessary for healing. In cases where irrigation-related injury is accompanied by persistent infection or structural damage, the prognosis for both primary treatment and retreatment becomes guarded, and extraction may represent the most predictable therapeutic option to ensure resolution of inflammation and prevention of further complications (Hülsmann et al. 2007). Neurological complications may occur following extrusion of root canal filling materials beyond the apical foramen, particularly when neural structures are involved. Rosen et al. (2016) demonstrated that such events can lead to transient or persistent sensory disturbances, with prognosis depending on the type and extent of extrusion, proximity to nerves, and timing of intervention. When material extrusion is associated with ongoing inflammation, pain, or neurosensory impairment, conservative management may be unpredictable, and extraction can be considered a justified therapeutic option to eliminate the source of neural irritation (Rosen et al. (2016)).

Recent advances in endodontic materials have focused on the introduction of premixed bioceramic sealers, which are designed to enhance sealing ability and promote favorable biological responses. In their scoping review, Wiśniewski et al. 2025 report that these materials exhibit bioactivity, dimensional stability, and antimicrobial properties, particularly when used in combination with warm obturation techniques (Wiśniewski et al. 2025). While such sealers may support periapical healing under ideal conditions, the authors also emphasize that their clinical performance remains highly dependent on proper canal preparation, controlled obturation, and anatomical considerations. Excessive heat application or unintended material extrusion may compromise surrounding tissues, reinforcing the importance of meticulous technique and careful case selection. Consequently, even with modern bioactive materials, technical and biological complications can persist, and in cases of structural compromise or uncontrolled extrusion, extraction may remain the most predictable therapeutic option (Wiśniewski et al. 2025). Complications related to root canal filling procedures represent a critical determinant of endodontic treatment outcome and long-term tooth survival. Obturation-related errors such as overfilling, underfilling, void formation, inadequate adaptation to canal walls, and extrusion of filling materials beyond the root canal system may compromise the apical seal, facilitate microbial persistence, and trigger

inflammatory or neurovascular reactions. The clinical impact of these complications is influenced not only by the properties of the obturation materials but also by canal anatomy, obturation technique, and operator control. When such factors converge and result in persistent symptoms, biological failure, or structural compromise that limits the predictability of retreatment, extraction may constitute a rational and definitive therapeutic option (6). The study by Jang et al. 2024 specifically addresses early failure following primary root canal treatment, which is a key upstream event in the clinical pathway that may ultimately lead to retreatment or tooth extraction. By identifying predictors of early endodontic failure—such as persistent symptoms, radiographic signs of unresolved periapical pathology, and treatment-related factors—the paper strengthens the concept that endodontic complications are often foreseeable and biologically driven, rather than random adverse events (Jang et al. 2024). In the context of your discussion, this article supports the idea that when early failure indicators are present, the prognosis for successful retreatment may be limited, particularly in the presence of technical complications or anatomical constraints. Consequently, extraction may represent a clinically justified and predictable therapeutic decision, rather than a treatment failure per se. The paper therefore aligns conceptually with the evidence you cite on post-endodontic extraction and complements the broader framework of complication-related outcomes discussed in the literature (Jang et al. 2024).

Materials and methods

A 48-year-old male patient, without reported concomitant systemic diseases, presented for dental consultation due to acute symptoms originating from tooth 47 (mandibular right second molar). The patient reported persistent, intense pain, described as continuous and poorly responsive to the intake of analgesic medication, with only minimal and transient relief. According to the patient's history, the symptoms had progressively intensified, prompting the emergency visit. Clinical and radiographic evaluation was performed to assess the source of pain. Radiographic examination revealed the presence of a composite

restoration extending deeply toward the distal pulp horn of tooth 47, suggesting close proximity to the pulp tissue. The radiographic findings, in conjunction with the clinical presentation, indicated a likely pulpal involvement associated with the existing restoration, consistent with the patient's acute symptomatology (Fig. 1).

Root canal treatment of tooth 47 was carried out over three clinical sessions. Under mandibular block anesthesia, access cavity preparation was performed during the first visit, followed by extirpation of the pulp tissue. After completion of chemomechanical preparation, calcium hydroxide [$\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$] was placed as an intracanal medicament, and the cavity was temporarily sealed. The medicament was maintained for a period of 10 days. At the second appointment, the intracanal dressing was removed, and following reassessment of the canals, calcium hydroxide was reapplied for an additional 10-day period (Fig. 2), aiming to enhance intracanal disinfection and control persistent microbial activity. During the third visit, after removal of the intracanal medicament and final canal preparation, the root canals were obturated using AH sealer in combination with a single-cone obturation technique. The quality and extent of the root canal filling were verified radiographically (Fig. 3).

Figure 1. Periapical x-ray detecting composite filling reaching to the distal pulp horn.

Figure 2. Medications used for the root canal treatment.

Figure 3. definitive root canal treatment and a temporary restoration.

Radiographic verification of the root canal obturation revealed the presence of a perforation with extrusion of the sealer into the periapical tissues of both roots. Following obturation, a temporary coronal restoration was placed, and a subsequent appointment was scheduled for definitive composite restoration. After placement of the permanent restoration, the tooth exhibited slight mobility, and the patient began to report persistent pain localized to the affected area. Despite conservative management, including systemic medication intake, the symptoms did not resolve within one week. Adjunctive supportive therapy was initiated, comprising physiotherapy and low-intensity periodontal laser treatment, aiming to reduce inflammation and promote tissue healing. However, the patient reported progressive worsening of symptoms, characterized by increasing pain intensity and gradually increasing tooth mobility and severe general discomfort.

Due to the unfavorable clinical evolution, a follow-up radiographic examination was performed (Fig. 4). The imaging revealed osteolytic changes in the periapical region, consistent with ongoing pathological bone resorption and further corroborating the deterioration of the local biological environment.

Given the progressive clinical deterioration and the lack of response to conservative management, extraction

Figure 4. An osteolytic process and a demarcation line around the affected tooth 47.

of tooth 47 was deemed the most appropriate therapeutic option. The patient was adequately informed about the indication for extraction and provided written informed consent prior to the procedure.

Intraoperative assessment demonstrated severe compromise of the periapical bone. As shown in Figs 5, 6, the residual bone surrounding the root apices exhibited sequestration, with a bone fragment that was loosely attached and could be detached with minimal resistance. The tooth was removed atraumatically, with minimal to no bleeding, and was extracted together with the associated bone sequestrum, which was subsequently separated easily from the root surface (Fig. 6), reflecting advanced localized bone necrosis.

Figure 5. Tooth 47 immediately after extraction.

Figure 6. Sequestrum detachment from the roots after extraction of the tooth.

Following extraction, a postoperative control radiograph was obtained to evaluate the extraction site and the surrounding bone structures (Fig. 7). The retrieved bone specimen was subsequently submitted for histological examination. After consultation with a maxillofacial surgeon, the patient was referred for further diagnostic evaluation. Granulated bone tissue corresponding to the sequestrum, along with adjacent soft tissue samples, was collected and preserved for biopsy and histopathological analysis, aiming to clarify the underlying nature of the observed bone alterations.

Figure 7. Control x-ray after tooth extraction.

Histological examination (No TL 144) confirmed the presence of granulation tissue associated with the bone sequestrum. Microscopic analysis revealed features consistent with a purulent inflammatory process surrounding foreign material, accompanied by a pronounced granulation tissue response. These findings corroborated the clinical and radiographic evidence of persistent inflammation and supported the diagnosis of an advanced inflammatory reaction in the periapical region.

The postoperative period was uneventful, with progressive resolution of symptoms. Healing was supported by systemic antibiotic therapy, administered according to standard postoperative protocols. No signs of infection, excessive bleeding, or delayed soft tissue healing were observed during follow-up visits, and the patient reported gradual relief of discomfort in the operated area. At three months post-extraction, a cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) scan was performed in connection with planned implant placement in the third quadrant. Radiographic evaluation demonstrated favorable bone healing, characterized by resolution of the previously observed osteolytic changes and evidence of bone regeneration at the extraction site (Fig. 8). These findings indicated a satisfactory healing response and adequate conditions for subsequent implant-related treatment planning.

Figure 8. CBCT verification of the bone healing.

Discussion

The present case highlights the clinical consequences of obturation-related complications, particularly root perforation and extrusion of endodontic materials into periapical tissues, which may initiate a sustained inflammatory cascade. In the reported patient, persistent pain, progressive mobility, and radiographic osteolysis indicated a failure of biological resolution despite intracanal medication, definitive obturation, and adjunctive conservative therapies. The intraoperative finding of a bone sequestrum, together with histological confirmation of a purulent inflammatory process surrounding foreign material, provides direct pathological evidence of an unfavorable tissue response. These observations align with contemporary evidence suggesting that, when foreign material-induced inflammation and structural compromise coexist, the prognosis of retreatment becomes unpredictable. In such situations, extraction should be regarded not as a treatment failure, but as a rational endpoint aimed at eliminating the source of inflammation and preventing further tissue destruction.

Long-term evidence further supports the notion that root canal treatment success and tooth preservation depend less on isolated technical variables and more on the overall biological and structural context of the treated tooth. In a 25-year cohort study, Van Nieuwenhuysen et al. 2023 demonstrated that sustained tooth survival is primarily influenced by persistent periapical health, structural integrity, and the ability to control infection over time, rather than by the endodontic procedure alone. These findings align with risk-based outcome models suggesting that when multiple unfavorable factors coexist—such as foreign material extrusion, progressive bone loss, and ongoing inflammation—the likelihood of long-term preservation decreases substantially. In the present case, the convergence of these determinants indicated a limited prognosis for further conservative management. Accordingly, extraction should be interpreted as a biologically justified and clinically responsible therapeutic endpoint, aimed at restoring local tissue stability and enabling predictable subsequent rehabilitation (Van Nieuwenhuysen et al. 2023). Long-term observational data further indicate that tooth survival after primary root canal treatment is primarily determined by sustained periapical health and structural stability over time. In a retrospective observation spanning 5 to 37 years, López-Valverde et al. 2023 demonstrated that teeth exhibiting persistent apical pathology or structural compromise showed a markedly reduced likelihood of long-term survival, irrespective of initial treatment success. These findings reinforce the concept that, in the presence of progressive biological deterioration, extraction may represent a clinically sound and prognostically justified endpoint rather than a failure of endodontic care (López-Valverde et al. 2023). Evidence from retreatment-focused cohorts further supports the need for careful prognostic assessment before pursuing additional conservative interventions. In a retrospective cohort study, Turan Gökdoğan et al. 2025 demonstrated that the long-term success and survival of non-surgical

root canal retreatment are strongly influenced by pre-existing periapical pathology, tooth type, structural integrity, and the presence of procedural complications. Importantly, the authors report substantially reduced predictability of retreatment outcomes when unfavorable biological and anatomical conditions coexist. In such scenarios, continued retreatment attempts may offer limited benefit, supporting extraction as a clinically justified and biologically sound alternative when infection control and tissue stability cannot be reliably achieved through conservative means, as also reflected in long-term outcome analyses (Turan Gökdoğan et al. 2025).

Anatomical complexity further contributes to the predictability of endodontic outcomes. In a retrospective analysis, Karobari et al. 2025 demonstrated that complex root canal morphology is significantly associated with increased rates of endodontic treatment failure, largely due to its influence on procedural errors and inadequate disinfection. These findings are particularly relevant in multi-rooted mandibular molars, where anatomical variations may predispose to complications such as perforation and obturation-related extrusion. In the present case, root morphology likely represented an additional contributing factor to the unfavorable biological response observed, reinforcing the multifactorial nature of treatment failure and the limited prognosis for conservative retreatment (Karobari et al. 2025).

Recent evidence further underscores the prognostic significance of unintentional sealer extrusion beyond the root canal system. In a retrospective cohort study, Bamrungwong et al. 2025 demonstrated that while limited extrusion may remain clinically asymptomatic in some cases, extensive extrusion—particularly when associated with persistent symptoms or periapical pathology—significantly compromises long-term outcomes. The authors identified ongoing inflammation and unfavorable biological responses to extruded material as key predictors of treatment failure. These observations closely mirror the clinical and histopathological findings of the present case and support the rationale that, when foreign material-induced inflammation persists, extraction may represent a biologically justified and prognostically sound therapeutic endpoint (Bamrungwong et al. 2025).

Procedural factors related to obturation technique also play a critical role in post-treatment outcomes. In a prospective randomized clinical study, Abada et al. 2025 demonstrated that different obturation techniques are associated with significantly varying rates of postobturation pain and sealer extrusion, indicating that material displacement beyond the apical confines is not solely material-dependent but also technique-sensitive. The authors reported that increased sealer extrusion correlated with higher incidence and persistence of postoperative discomfort. These findings support the clinical course observed in the present case, where obturation-related extrusion was followed by sustained pain and progressive inflammatory changes, further reinforcing the limited predictability of conservative management once foreign material-induced tissue reactions are established (Abada et al. 2025).

Taken together, the present case supports the concept that endodontic treatment failure and subsequent extraction are the result of a cumulative burden of unfavorable biological, anatomical, and treatment-related factors, rather than an isolated procedural error. Consistent with predictive models of endodontic failure, such as those described by Herbst et al. 2022, the coexistence of obturation-related perforation, extrusion of foreign material, progressive bone destruction, and persistent symptoms indicated a limited prognosis for conservative retreatment (Herbst et al. 2022). In this context, extraction should be regarded as a deliberate therapeutic endpoint, aimed at definitive infection control and biological stabilization, rather than as an indicator of endodontic incompetence. This case emphasizes the importance of early risk recognition, realistic prognostic assessment, and timely intervention in preventing further tissue damage and facilitating subsequent rehabilitative treatment.

Conclusion

This case illustrates a severe post-endodontic complication characterized by obturation-related perforation, extrusion of sealing material into the periapical tissues, and progressive local bone destruction. Despite staged endodontic treatment and subsequent conservative supportive measures, the clinical course was marked by persistent pain, increasing tooth mobility, and radiographically evident osteolysis. Extraction of the affected tooth revealed advanced periapical bone sequestration, which was confirmed histologically as a purulent inflammatory process associated with foreign material. These findings underscore that, in selected cases, extraction represents a justified and definitive therapeutic solution when endodontic complications compromise both biological healing and structural integrity.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Faculty of Dental Medicine.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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